

Poetry, work and life: interview with portuguese writer Pedro Lopes Adão /

Poesia, ofício e vida: entrevista com o escritor Pedro Lopes Adão

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Pedro Lopes Adão was born on October 4, 2001, in the center of Porto and currently lives in Rio Tinto, Gondomar (Portugal). He began his writing career at the age of 15, starting his journey with poetry and later moving on to literary criticism. She has already had the opportunity to collaborate with various cultural media, such as *Devaneio* magazine, of which she is a member of the editorial board, *Comunidade Cultura & Arte*, *Kametsa* magazine, *Mirada* magazine, *Ruído Manifesto*, among others. After joining the Faculty of Letters of the University of Porto, he was invited to make himself known in *Revista Alegre* and to be part of the anthology “*110 Anos, 110 poetas*” (org. Isabel Morujão). He is the author of the books: *Palavra em Queda*, ed. Glaciar (2022) and *Os Amorosos & Os Odiados*, ed. Lema d'Origem (2023) and *Ars Longa, Vita Brevis*, ed. Glaciar (2023). He recently organized and coordinated the book *Alguns ensaios de quê? - Em homenagem a Ana Luísa Amaral*, ed. Lema d'Origem (2023). He is currently a columnist for *Ruído Manifesto* magazine.

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1) You study, write and work with literature. What was your encounter with the world of literature like?

It was an encounter between poetry and philosophy, a symbiosis that galloped gradually; I can't say that I was dedicated from birth - there were nuances, according to reports that came back to me from my childhood -: adolescence brought enthusiasm, curiosity.

2) Why do you write?

I write because I feel the need to convey a message. What message? I believe it may be the answer to the anxiety of souls, the word that shelters silence, discovering that word. And I do it unmotivated by any other purpose than that, because I understand that nothing else is in store for me apart from these gigantic tasks.

3) Which writers inspire you?

All the decadentists and symbolists! More recently, I've been following the metaphysical path. I started with António Nobre and now I'm very slowly working my way through the two volumes of Fernando Echevarría's *Obra Inacabada*, which is study material for a lifetime.

4) Tell us about your first book, *Palavra em Queda* (2022). What was the writing process like? What themes do you deal with? Where can we buy it?

It was born out of my paradox of organization. I never thought it was possible to organize a book of poetry, since it has an inherent breathiness. *Palavra em Queda* (The Falling Word) came about through an inner question of which are the right words, which words say what needs to be said, using memory and the questioning of existence as vehicles. His poems ended up being written in meditation on these angles, one by one or a handful in bursts, but always with the labor of revision and study, because poetry needs this fermentation. It is available in all bookstores in Portugal, both physical and digital.

5) Comment on *Os Amorosos & Os Odiados* (2023). What is the motto of this book? Where can we buy it?

The main concern of this book is to highlight the female figure and place it on a higher level. All the male quadrants, pictorially versed as lovers, poets, widowers, etc., are placed on the step of those who contemplate and suffer, those who have suffered, by a vague or concrete pillar of the feminine. It's a book concerned with the ambiguity of two relational elements, love and hate, without one overpowering the other. It is available in all digital bookstores in Portugal.

6) What about your most recent book, *Ars Longa, Vita Brevis* (2023)? Explain the title and its implications for the meaning/proposal of the work, and where we can buy it.

The title is the inversion of an aphorism by Hippocrates, which translates to "Art is long, life is short", and allows for a dialog with the book in a more metaphysical sense; it is, in fact, my debut in metaphysical poetry, dialoguing with religion and proposing new meanings to some symbols, such as the Apostles, for example. It's available in all physical and digital bookstores in Portugal.

7) Tell us about your new book of poetry, due to be published in 2024. What will the theme be? What should readers expect?

I don't want to get ahead of myself. They should expect a few poems so that I can take a break for a long study, a poetic renewal within myself.

8) You're currently a columnist for *Ruído Manifesto* magazine. What topics will you be covering in this new publication?

I'm going to publish all the Portuguese authors who, inside or outside the canon, have enriched my country and are perhaps little talked about. It will be a corner of justice, of revitalization.

9) Talk about your other projects in the field of literature and culture, such as anthologies of academic essays.

It's a new phase of my life in literature. There is an inefficiency in the Portuguese Academy in dealing with certain authors and themes, which has been harmful to culture in the medium and long term. These anthologies come about with the aim of inviting young authors and specialists to study a theme and bring a book to press that can benefit the curious reader and the student - it's a form of public service without state aid.

10) You recently organized and coordinated the book *Alguns ensaios de quê? - Em homenagem a Ana Luísa Amaral* (2023). This book has had great repercussions in academic circles and is already in the collections of several libraries around the world. Tell us about this positive feedback.

It's a mixed bag to answer this question. Fourteen major universities around the world already have it, plus a few town halls in Portugal. In fact, I didn't expect it to be so popular because it was a huge risk to publish a book of academic essays, which, according to publishing dictates, sells as little as poetry and theater. Apparently we bucked the trend and I received a few messages saying that I had helped someone with their research, in other words, mission accomplished.